

EFFECTIVE METHODS AND STRATEGIES FOR TEACHING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN MULTI-LEVEL GROUPS

Mukhammadiyeva Shakhzoda Farkhodovna

Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

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Abstract: The subject of the study in this paper is the teaching of a foreign language in multilevel groups. The purpose of the article is to analyze the teaching foreign language in heterogeneous groups. The author considers the existing scientific approaches to the definition of the concept of "heterogeneous group". Then examines the reasons for the emergence of this method of teaching, its weaknesses and strengths. The most common problems that arise for students and teachers in such groups are also given. Particular attention in the study is paid to the consideration of methods and strategies work in heterogeneous groups, as well as methods of control and evaluation of students' knowledge. The author comes to the conclusion that despite certain difficulties in working in such groups, with a comprehensive approach of the educational institution to adapting the program materials to the needs of students with different levels of foreign language proficiency training in a heterogeneous group can be effective.

Keywords: Foreign language, foreign language teaching, foreign language learning, heterogeneous group, multilevel group, teaching methodology.

Introduction: The relevance of the study is determined by the fact that, as a rule, when forming groups to study a foreign language, the students' current level of proficiency in the language being studied. This practice has a number of obvious advantages both for foreign language learners and for the teacher. However, in many countries of the world, including Uzbekistan, many teachers are forced to work in multi-level groups. Often teachers find themselves in a difficult situation because they have no experience of working with heterogeneous groups. It is work in such groups that this article is devoted to. The aim of the research is to analyze heterogeneous groups, as well as to identify the most effective methods of teaching, knowledge control and assessment of students of multilevel groups. This paper will consider the definition of multilevel (heterogeneous) group, the typology, the reasons emergence, pros and cons, as well as frequent difficulties, caused by this form of learning, along with methods and strategies for teaching foreign languages in multi-level groups, as well as approaches to assessment of students.

The main objectives of this article are to study the existing definitions of the term "multi-level group"; analyze the methods of practical work with such groups, available in a foreign technique; special attention is paid to the approaches to assessment of students within a multi-level group.

In the process of working on this article, the following research methods were used: analysis of scientific, pedagogical and methodological literature.

The scientific novelty of the article is determined by the analysis of foreign techniques work in heterogeneous groups. This approach is justified by the fact that in recent decades, due to several large waves of migration, many educational institutions specializing in foreign language teaching have been forced to turn to teaching students in large multilevel groups. Because of this, foreign methodologists and practicing teachers have done a great deal of work

to improve methods and strategies for working in heterogeneous groups. Therein lies the theoretical significance of the article.

The practical significance is manifested in the possibility of using the results of this study in the practical work not only of higher education institutions, which most often use this method of teaching, but also other educational institutions.

Some linguists and methodologists believe that there are no completely homogeneous groups of students, because in all groups the level of proficiency in different kinds of speech (speaking, reading, listening, and writing) is different in all groups [1-16]. However, it is worth distinguishing the groups in which the level of students varies from the groups where there are students with a significant difference in the level of foreign language proficiency. According to researchers, a group is considered multilevel, or multilevel, if students' level of a foreign language differs by 2 levels or by 2 years of foreign language study. For example, Mathews, Aydinley, and Van Horn give the following definition of a multilevel group: "...groups in which students with a large difference in foreign language proficiency level, from beginning to advanced" [2]. In addition to the difference in the level of foreign or individual types of speech, N. Hess also highlights differences in the characters, age, learning style of students, attitude towards learning, their ethno-cultural background [3, p. 2]. Lightbown and Spada agree with Hess, who note that there are certain character traits that either help or hinder successful learning of students [16].

In the study of any phenomenon it is necessary to examine the causes of its occurrence. In the case of multilevel groups, the causes are heterogeneous. Among them we can name the following:

- Lack of administrative resources. For example, in sparsely populated areas, schools do not have the opportunity to create separate groups for each levels;
- the philosophy of the educational institution. In this case, the groups of the educational institution intentionally form groups at different levels in order to emphasize the continuity and continuity of the learning process;
- insufficient elaboration of the program;
- the student's wish. For certain reasons, especially if the foreign language is not a major subject, the student may be forced to study in a group level that he or she does not meet;
- the curriculum of the educational institution.

The study of any phenomenon requires not only a review of definitions, identifying the reasons for its occurrence, but also an analysis of the strengths and weaknesses of the subject of study. Multilevel foreign language groups are no exception. Such groups provoke a number of difficulties both for students and for the teacher:

- Students with a low level of proficiency in the language being studied feel insecure and anxious. The situation can have a negative impact on their motivation and subsequent learning outcomes;
- Students with a high level of proficiency may feel bored and, as a result, lose motivation for learning.

For the teacher, working in multilevel groups also entails a number of difficulties:

- First of all, it requires more work from the teacher to prepare materials of different levels for each lesson. This takes more time, which causes fatigue. Taken together, all of the above points can lead to emotional burnout, among other things. To avoid emotional burnout,

according to Hess's recommendation, it is worth remembering that "a teacher cannot be everywhere and always, and cannot meet all the urgent needs of all students in the group". [3, c. 10];

- if the curriculum is not adapted to the needs and abilities students with different levels of proficiency in a foreign language, the teacher has to select additional materials for each lesson independently;
- the organization of the work of students (subgroups of students) with different levels;
- the teacher has to choose additional materials for each lesson by himself/herself; organization of work of students (groups of students of different levels) can be complicated and cause the loss of control over the group;
- the teacher has to devote less time to each subgroup [4];
- no less serious challenge for the teacher of a heterogeneous group is the difficulty in organizing an individual approach to each student, because, as a rule, heterogeneous groups are numerous.

As mentioned earlier, both strong and weak students in a heterogeneous group can be demotivated. In this situation, the instructor is forced to look for new ways to motivate them [5, p. 92-93].

It is no less of a challenge for the teacher of a multilevel group to monitor and evaluate their knowledge. The significant difference in the level of foreign language skills, combined with different experiences in the study and the objectives of teaching is very difficult to develop a system of control and evaluation of knowledge and skills of students. In addition, of great importance for effective learning in mixed groups plays introductory testing, which is often neglected in educational institutions with multilevel groups. Accurate and correct assessment of each student's initial level is essential to both the development teaching strategies for each individual student and for the group as a whole.

The main paradigm of work in a multilevel group is the change of the role of the teacher in learning process; he or she becomes a facilitator-assistant, coordinator, whose main role is to guide students in their independent study of material. Thus, it becomes evident that the role of a teacher changes after the role of a student. The student should take more responsibility for the process of his learning [6; 7].

Despite a certain change in the role of the teacher in the learning process, it should not be assumed that the amount of teacher's work decreases. On the contrary, the amount of extracurricular work is growing, because the teacher has to develop a strategy and choose the methods and techniques of teaching that allow create all the conditions for students with different levels of foreign language proficiency to work together.

Strategies for Multilevel Groups

The teacher is required to supervise the group on a permanent basis, obligatorily assess the level of students at the initial stage, to provide continuous improvement of the level of students, to create a comfortable atmosphere for all, selecting appropriate materials and adapting them to the different levels of students in the group.

However, there is no consensus in the scientific and pedagogical community on the need to adapt the course materials to the level of each student. A number of researchers (Tomlinson, Lightbown, and Spada) consider such a strategy unreasonable [8, p. 4; 9, pp. 28-29]. Tomlinson emphasizes that the preparation of individual assignments for each class for each

student deprives the class of integrity and reduces the effectiveness of the learning process, and the mastering of the necessary skills will be extremely fragmented. Tomlinson summarizes that while differential instruction requires that students' individual characteristics be taken into account, it certainly does not involve individual assignments for everyone. The instructor's job is to form a selection of assignments that allows all students to be to be involved in the learning process. The instructor should plan lessons in a way that sometimes works with the whole group, sometimes with mini-groups, and sometimes with individual students. As a result, the group becomes a close-knit group, and the instructor has the opportunity to monitor the progress of each student, and even students can see their progress. It is also worth offer more open-ended assignments that allow each students to give an answer within the limits of their level of vocabulary and grammar knowledge.

At the same time, when developing tactics for working with a heterogeneous group, the instructor should not vary the number and volume of assignments depending on the level of students. For example, giving advanced students more assignments can only lead to the fact that students will consider it a punishment and, as a result, they will lose motivation to further improve their level of foreign language proficiency. Thus, it will be much more effective to differentiate not the number of tasks, but the essence of the task itself according to needs of students at a certain level [8, p. 6-7].

Salva in the article recommends that teachers use in the classroom the same text, but adapted to different levels of students. In the same way texts should be adapted in the same way. Materials can be both prepared texts can be prepared independently or suitable ones can be selected from specialized resources [9].

When working with heterogeneous groups no less complicated process, along with the selection and adaptation of materials and lesson planning, is the assessment of the students. Unfortunately, this list of the learning process has not been given much attention by the academic community. In her work the author considered several methods proposed in the scientific literature.

Certainly, in each session in mixed-level groups, the instructor observes each student and his or her progress, but summative assessment and evaluation of results can be a challenge for the instructor.

This is because the institution's administration and curriculum usually require that all students be evaluated on a single test, regardless of the level of each individual student. Rarer is the situation in which the instructor is required to develop an individualized curriculum and to assess each student on a regular basis.

Heid Spruck Wrigley argues that student assessment should consist of two mandatory steps: 1) introductory testing to determine the student's current student's level and understanding of learning objectives, as well as ongoing tracking of progress [10].

Specialists attach considerable importance to student self-assessment as well, not only and not so much in the final assessment, but also directly in the learning process. With the help of tasks with the possibility of self-testing, students can regularly monitor their progress and learning outcomes.

Also in the learning process, the so-called "peer assessment" has proven itself well. The assessment of students with lower levels by their peers with higher levels of proficiency, has also worked well in the learning process. Specifically, in a 2011 study. Hantow and Pavlov say

that in heterogeneous groups, surveyed students with low levels of foreign language proficiency considered their advanced-level classmates to be excellent facilitators of the learning process. Interviewees noted that assessment by their peers was a motivating factor [11, p. 16].

In his book, J. Tice suggests that in students' final evaluations the test work should be differentiated, that is, it should be designed so that the level of difficulty of the tasks increases both in each individual test item, and in general as students complete the work. Thus, both weak, and strong students will get a task that corresponds to their level of foreign language proficiency [12, p. 75-76].

An integral part of the students' assessment is their evaluation. In the process of assessing students in a multilevel group the teacher should choose a method of evaluation of students' knowledge that would be the most objective and accurate. Unfortunately, it should be noted that in scientific literature the methods of evaluating the knowledge and skills of students are not given as much attention. Several approaches to assessment methods are suggested by Tomlison in works from 2005 and 2017. [8, pp. 159-163; 13, pp. 93-97], who believes that grading students is partly a relic, and the whole system needs to be changed, because although it is the most understandable for students (and their parents) form of "feedback" of student and teacher, it does not fulfill its motivating functions, especially in a multilevel group. The results of the learning process are not only not motivating for weak students, but are even on the contrary - has a demotivating character. That is, in a situation where a student, who according to the results of the introductory test showed a low level of the language, made more progress by the end of the course than the student the results of the introductory testing. The objectivity of the assessment based on the level of foreign language proficiency in the final test cannot but be questioned. The evaluation system should be reformed not only to increase objectivity of the evaluation system but also to avoid transformation of the learning process into a learning process.

Tomlison describes several approaches to assessing students, such as: 2-Ps. system 2 grading methods (personal and accepted scale), portfolio method, the 3-Ps system (performane, process, progress).

Some of the approaches described seem impracticable, For example, when evaluating students of higher education institutions. For example, double grading, where the first grade is presented in numeric/letter equivalent, according to the scale adopted by the institution, and the second is an additional index characterizing the student's work, where 1 is work above the first grade level, 2 is work at grade level, and 3 is work below grade level.

Thus, a student who received a 5/3 worked well, but his or her level of does not generally correspond to the grade level, that is, the student received an "excellent" grade received an "advanced" grade.

Tomlinson also recommends using the principle of the 3 "P's" in grading: performance, process, progress. The instructor assigns 3 grades based on analysis of the following indicators of student performance: performance (results shown in tests and other types of work), process (attitude towards learning), progress (progress towards achieving the goals set by the teacher). According to Tomlinson, such approach allows weak students to focus on the growth and development of foreign and not just on the results (scores); at the same time, strong students, getting high current scores do not lose motivation, because with the

implementation of this approach getting a higher score without growth over their own level is not possible. Tomlinson cautions against giving an average score based on the sum of the 3 grades received, because 1 grade is inaccurate and reduces the objectivity of evaluation.

Another method of assessment suggested by Tomlinson is the portfolio approach. In this approach, each student maintains a portfolio of his or her work, from introductory testing to the student's best work for the period being assessed. In this way, both the learner and the teacher and, for example, the learner's parents the learner can see his work in development, which makes the final grades more objective and clear [8; 13].

According to the results of the study, we can conclude that in modern pedagogy the method of teaching foreign languages in multilevel groups occupies not the last place. The reasons for its implementation are different: administrative decision, insufficient teaching staff, large of students, for example, due to migration processes. Often the work in heterogeneous groups greatly complicates the teacher's work, It requires a lot of extra work. However a complex approach by the administration of an educational institution to adapt the curriculum materials to the educational needs of students and by the use of definite strategies and methods of teaching the educational process. The process may be no less effective than when working in a group with students at the same level.

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